

IMPACT OF EDUCATIONAL HEALTH INTERVENTION ON THE LIFESTYLE OF PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC HEART FAILURE: PRELIMINARY ANALYSIS

IMPACTO DA INTERVENÇÃO EDUCACIONAL EM SAÚDE NO ESTILO DE VIDA DE PACIENTES COM INSUFICIÊNCIA CARDÍACA CRÔNICA: ANÁLISE PRELIMINAR

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Abstract

Introduction: Heart failure (HF) is a disorder in which the heart is unable to supply the body's needs, causing a reduction in blood flow. Some comorbidities are associated, being more prevalent in the elderly. In this context, the health education program was created, which consists of guidance to improve the lifestyle, as health education and promotion of quality of life is fundamental. **Aims:** To evaluate the impact of the health education program on the lifestyle of patients with HF. **Methodology:** Cross-sectional, quantitative study with participants in an Interdisciplinary Cardiorespiratory Rehabilitation Program. **Results:** 20 questionnaires adapted from Nahas were carried out, in person, before and after meetings, with 10 patients. In the preventive components, food and medication use, 100% of the patients had a satisfactory lifestyle, 80% and 90% of the patients had an adequate lifestyle in the components of physical activity and stress control, respectively. **Conclusion:** In this preliminary sample, we can conclude that the patients participating in the Program have an adequate lifestyle.

Keywords: Heart failure, quality of life, health education.